

ASSESSMENT OF PATHOGENIC BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM SOIL ALONG ZAMFARAWA RIVER JEGA, KEBBI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to assess the pathogenic bacteriological quality of soil in Zamfarawa Farms Jega town. A total of 9 samples from three different farms were collected. Total plate count was used in isolating the pathogenic bacteria, biochemical tests also were carried out to identify the bacteria and conventional PCR technique was used in detecting the DNA of the isolated bacteria.

At the end of the study, three bacteria were isolated Bacillus cereus (44%) , Listeria monocytogenes with (44%) and Bacillus subtilis (11%), which indicates that agricultural practices, hygiene, fertilizing, and irrigation could be the source of contamination of soil used today for agricultural purposes. The use of untreated wastewater and water supplies contaminated with sewage for irrigation or untreated organic manure may be one of the important sources of pathogenic microorganisms.

INTRODUCTION

The soil around high-production farms is frequently contaminated with microbes, with arable lands and pastures being polluted by the feces of sick animals, which greatly contributes to the spread of patho-

ens (Trawińska et al., 2006). The use of manure as a fertilizer on fields necessitates adherence to an appropriate withdrawal period; failure to observe this period can result in a significant introduction of patho-

pathogenic bacteria into the soil, posing a considerable epidemiological risk (Amin et al., 2013). High temperatures and moisture levels enhance the survival of microorganisms in soil (Ngole et al., 2006). Utilizing manure piles from infected animals for fertilization can lead to soil contamination with pathogenic microorganisms (Petkov et al., 2006). Pathogenic strains of *E. coli* isolated from avian organic fertilizers have been found to cause human infections (Puno-Sarmiento et al., 2014).

METHODOLOGY

STUDY AREA

The study was conducted in Jega, a local government area in Kebbi State, Nigeria, located in the extreme northwestern corner of the country, between latitudes 10° to 15°N and longitudes 3° to 6°E. The state borders Benin Republic to the west, Niger Republic to the north, Sokoto State to the east, and Niger State to the south. The local government covers an area of 891 square kilometers and is bordered to the east by Aliero Local Government (Uzondu, 2008). The warmest months are April and May, with an average noon temperature of 40.3°C, while December is the coolest month with an average nighttime temperature of 16.2°C. The Zamfara River runs through Jega town, where local farms are situated. Residents use the river for various activities, including swimming, bathing, washing vehicles, fishing, farming, and animal rearing, which are common practices in the area (Uzondu, 2008).

SAMPLING DESIGN

A systematic sampling method was employed, where Three samples were collected from farms in the study area, specifically from farms one, three, and Five. Three soil samples from each farm were then

transferred to the Microbiology Laboratory at Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero, for analysis.

SAMPLE COLLECTION

Soil samples were collected from farms in Jega Local Government. The samples were labeled according to their collection site, with Three randomly located topsoil samples (7.5 cm depth) taken using an auger with an 8.5 cm diameter. The samples were placed in polyethylene bags and transported to the Microbiology Laboratory at Kebbi State University of Science and Technology, Aliero, for analysis.

SAMPLE PROCESSING

Soil sample processing involved weighing one gram of the soil suspension, which was serially diluted (ten-fold) and used to estimate aerobic heterotrophic bacterial populations using the standard spread-plate dilution method as described by Seeley and VanDemark (1981). This was done in triplicate. Nutrient agar containing 0.015% (w/v) nystatin (to inhibit fungal growth) was used for bacterial isolation, and incubation was carried out at 35°C for 24 hours. The identification of isolates was based on cultural, microscopic, and biochemical characteristics, with reference to Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology (1989).

CHARACTERISTICS OF BACTERIA ISOLATES

- Indole Test: Bacterial growth was inoculated into 5ml of peptone water and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Kovac's reagent (3-8 drops) was added and gently shaken. A red or pink color in the reagent layer within one minute indicates a positive reaction, while a yellow color indicates a negative reaction (APHA, 1998).

- Methyl Red-Voges Proskauer Test: Five mL of MR-VP broth was inoculated with the test organism and incubated at 35°C for 48-72 hours. One mL of the broth was transferred into a small serological tube, and 2-3 drops of methyl red were added. A red color indicates a positive methyl red test, while a yellow color indicates a negative test. For the VP test, 5 drops of 40% potassium hydroxide (KOH) were added to the remaining broth, followed by 15 drops of 5% naphthol in ethanol. The tube was shaken, loosened, and placed in a sloping position. A positive VP test is indicated by the development of a red color at the liquid-air interface within one hour, while no color change indicates a negative result (Krieg & Holt, 1994).
- Urease Test: Urea agar slopes were inoculated with the test organisms and incubated at 37°C for 48 hours. A positive reaction is indicated by the development of a bright pink or red color (Krieg & Holt, 1994).
- Triple-Sugar Iron Agar Test: A sterile needle was used to obtain the test organism, streaking the surface of the slant and stabbing it twice. The cap was loosely closed and incubated at 35°C for 24 hours (Krieg & Holt, 1994).

IDENTIFICATION OF THE MICROBIAL ISOLATES

The pure isolates found in the soil samples underwent microscopic observation, Gram staining, and standard biochemical tests according to the schemes of Benson (2002) and Cheesbrough (2006). The observed results were compared with those of known taxa using Cheesbrough (2006) and Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology by Holt et al. (1994). Using the Gram reaction,

Gram-positive organisms were streaked on mannitol salt agar plates and incubated inverted at 37°C for 24 hours. The presence of yellowish pigments in Mannitol Salt Agar indicates *Staphylococcus aureus* (Kigigha & Baraseibai, 2017). Tubes with color change and gas production were shaken and streaked in Levine's eosin methylene blue (EMB) agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. *E. coli* was indicated by the presence of small nucleated colonies with a greenish metallic sheen (Benson, 2002; Pepper & Gerba, 2005). Blood agar was used to streak the colonies; the presence of swarming growth and hemolytic properties on the medium after incubation indicates *Proteus* species and *Streptococcus* species, respectively (Kigigha & Baraseibai, 2017). *Salmonella* and *Shigella* species were indicated by the presence of black and pink colonies on *Salmonella-Shigella* agar (Odu & Adeniji, 2013). A triple sugar iron agar was prepared into slants, and the colonies were transferred into the slants. The presence of cracks and blackening of the medium confirmed a positive tube (Izah, 2015).

CONVENTIONAL PCR PROCEDURE PCR REQUIREMENTS NEED

Four components (reagents or chemicals) were obtained for the PCR process:

A bacterial DNA sample from the isolates
DNA primers: short single-stranded DNA that promotes synthesis of a complementary strand of nucleotides

DNA polymerase: an enzyme that aids in the synthesis of a complementary strand of DNA

Nucleotide solution mix containing adenine (A), thymidine (T), cytosine (C), and guanine (G) used to build duplicate DNA strands

The PCR process has 4 steps: collection, preparation, amplification, and post PCR clean-up. The PCR machine steps happen in the amplification step. segment of a DNA sample was placed in a suitable tube along with the reagents and chemicals listed above. The tube is placed into the PCR machine or thermal cycler. The thermal cycler takes the solution through a 3-step process: denaturation, annealing, and extension (Siebert, 2006).

Analysis with Electrophoresis
Electrophoresis.

Once the PCR process is completed, the resulting amplified (replicated) segments generated were compared to other nucleotide segments from a known source. The PCR-generated nucleotide sequences are then placed next to known nucleotide sequences from pathogens, or other sources in a separating gel. Electrical current is then run through the gel, and the various nucleotide sequences within the gel form bands that resemble a ladder, according to their electrical charge and molecular size.

This is termed gel electrophoresis. Bands or ladder-like steps that migrate to the same levels in the gel show identity of nucleotide sequences. This method is one of the most popular ways PCR tests are completed.

RESULT

Table 1 Viable plate count for soil from farm one

Sample	Dilution factor	Colony count/cfu/g	Mean±SD
Soil	10 ⁵	5	3.33±
	10 ⁶	3	1.53cfu/g
	10 ⁷	2	

Table 2 Viable plate count for soil from farm two

Sample	Dilution factor	Colony count/cfu/g	Mean±SD
Soil	10 ⁵	5	3.67±
	10 ⁶	3	1.42cfu/g
	10 ⁷	3	

Table 3 Viable plate count for soil from farm three

Sample	Dilution factor	Colony count/cfu/g	Mean±SD
Soil	10 ⁵	8	5.00±
	10 ⁶	5	3.00cfu/g
	10 ⁷	2	

Table 4 Morphological characteristics of isolated bacteria from sample from farm one

Sample	Size	Colour	Gram Stain	Shape	Arrangements	Spore
Soil	Rhizoid	Milk	+	Rod	In chain	Central Spore
	Large	Milk	+	Rod	Single	
	Large	Milk	+	Rod	Paires	No Spore

Table 5 Morphological characteristics of isolated bacteria from soil sample from farm two

Sample	Size	Colour	Gram Stain	Shape	Arrangements	Spore
Soil	Rhizoid	Milk	+	Rod	In chain	Central Spore
	Large	Milk	+	Rod	Single	
	Rhizoid	Milk	+	Rod	In chain	

Table 6 Morphological characteristics of isolated bacteria from soil sample from farm three

Sample	Size	Colour	Gram Stain	Shape	Arrangements	Spore
Soil	Large	White	+	Rod	Single	Central Spore
	Rhizoid	Milk	+	Rod	In chain	Central Spore
	Large	Milk	+	Rod	Single	

Table 7 Identified bacteria isolated from soil sample of farm one

S/N	Isolate	Gram/Shape	Cat	Ura	Cit	Mr	Vp	Ind	H2s	Gas	mot	Glu	Lac	Suc	Spo	Sta	Identified Bacteria
1	SLW	G+ Rod	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	Basilus cereus
2	SSM	G+ Rod	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	L. Monocytogenes
3	SLM	G+ Rod	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	B. Subtilis

Table 8 Identified bacteria isolated from soil sample of farm two

S/N	Isolate	Gram/Shape	Cat	Ura	Cit	Mr	Vp	Ind	H2s	Gas	mot	Glu	Lac	Suc	Spo	Sta	Identified Bacteria
4	SLW	G+ Rod	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	Basilus cereus
5	SSM	G+ Rod	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	L. Monocytogenes
6	SLM	G+ Rod	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	B. Subtilis

Table 9 Identified bacteria isolated from soil sample of farm three

S/N	Isolate	Gram/Shape	Cat	Ura	Cit	Mr	Vp	Ind	H2s	Gas	mot	Glu	Lac	Suc	Spo	Sta	Identified Bacteria
7	SLW	G+ Rod	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	Basilus cereus
8	SSM	G+ Rod	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	L. Monocytogenes
9	SLM	G+ Rod	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	B. Subtilis

Table 10 Percentage of occurrences of bacteria isolated in soil sample from three different farms

M/O	F1/S1	F1/S2	F1/S3	F2/S1	F2/S2	F2/S3	F3/S1	F3/S2	F3/S3	
S. aureus										0%
S. typhi										0%
E. coli										0%
Basilus cereus	+			+		+	+			44%
L. monocytogenes		+			+			+	+	44%
Basillus subtilis			+							11%

KEY

F1/S1 = Farm one/Soil sample one

DISCUSSION

This study highlights that the pathogenic bacteria in the soil at Zamfarawa River in Jega are a significant cause of various foodborne infections in the community. Different bacterial species, including *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, and *Listeria monocytogenes*, were detected in the collected samples. Out of nine samples collected, each was found to contain some species of pathogenic bacteria, predominantly spore-forming *Bacillus* species, though some non-spore-forming bacteria were also present. These findings align with the studies of Ezeronye (2005) and Adesemoye et al. (2006). The presence of *Bacillus* species is recognized as common and persistent in soil environments (Rabah et al., 2010). The contamination of the soil could be attributed to the discharge of large quantities of animal excreta in the effluent, which contains *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Bacillus* species, and *Salmonella* species. Similar findings have been reported by Ezeronye and Ubalua (2005), Bala (2006), and Rabah et al. (2010). *Bacillus cereus* and *Listeria monocytogenes* had the highest occurrence at 44%, while *Bacillus subtilis* had an 11% occurrence. This study correlates with research conducted in Spain, where a lower detection rate of *L. monocytogenes* was reported in 0.7% of samples (Abadias et al., 2018). Some of the bacterial isolates identified in this study have been associated with several diseases, such as diarrhea caused by *E. coli*, *Enterobacter*, and *Salmonella* species, as well as infectious diseases including gastroenteritis, typhoid fever, and dysentery (Nwidu et al., 2008), and urinary tract infections. The presence of these bacterial isolates suggests that the water sources in this area are not safe for consumption (Aku-

buenyi et al., 2013).

CONCLUSION

This study assessed the presence of pathogenic bacteria in soil. The findings underscore the need for increased research on this topic in Jega town. The results indicate that agricultural practices, hygiene, fertilization, and irrigation could be contributing to the contamination of soil currently used for farming. The use of untreated wastewater and water contaminated with sewage for irrigation, or untreated organic manure, may be key sources of pathogenic microorganisms contaminating the soil, as evidenced by the detection of various pathogenic bacterial species in the samples.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study's results and conclusions, the following recommendations are suggested to reduce soil contamination: Agricultural practices should be reviewed, and strict regulations should be implemented, particularly regarding the use of safe irrigation water and fertilizers. Alternative irrigation methods should be explored to reduce reliance on river water, which often contains surface runoff, the primary source of contamination. Additionally, other sources of manure should be considered for fertilizing crops. Further studies are recommended to explore other irrigation methods, as well as the impact on vegetables and other areas.

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